

Peer-reviewed academic journal

**Innovative Issues and Approaches in
Social Sciences**

IIASS VOLUME 15 (2022)

Innovative Issues and Approaches in Social Sciences

IIASS is a double blind peer review academic journal published 3 times yearly (January, May, September) covering different social sciences: political science, sociology, economy, public administration, law, management, communication science, psychology and education.

IIASS has started as a Sldip – Slovenian Association for Innovative Political Science journal and is being published by ERUDIO Center for Higher Education.

Typeset

This journal was typeset in 11 pt. Arial, Italic, Bold, and Bold Italic; the headlines were typeset in 14 pt. Arial, Bold

Abstracting and Indexing services

COBISS, International Political Science Abstracts, CSA Worldwide Political Science Abstracts, CSA Sociological Abstracts, PAIS International, DOAJ, Google scholar.

Publication Data:

ERUDIO Education Center

Innovative issues and approaches in social sciences, 2022,
vol. 15

ISSN 1855-0541

Additional information: www.iiass.com

RESEARCH ON JOBS AND WORKING CONDITIONS OF INSPECTION AND HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGER

Djordje Nadrljanski¹, Irena Masce², Mira Pavlinovic³

Abstract

The tasks of inspection and personnel management are mainly related to tasks connected with control: transport documents, loading and unloading of cargo, agency tariffs, etc. The goal of this research is the measurement of business creativity and the development of a creative organizational climate in the field of inspection and personnel management in maritime affairs. The research sample was picked from all inspection and personnel managers in the maritime sector and was identified by random extraction by the method of systematic sampling. The results of this research show that inspection and personnel management is largely dissatisfied with current organizational practices and are therefore relatively often focused on adopting modern approaches to improving the effectiveness of inspection and personnel management.

Keywords: inspection and personnel management tasks, maritime industry, working conditions, survey

Introduction

Inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs are employed after completing their studies at the College of Inspection and Personnel Management. The rights and duties of inspectors for inspection and personnel management are related to activities on land.

¹ Prof.dr.sc.Djordje - Nadrljanski Visoka škola ARCA, Dekan@visokaskolaarca

² Irena Mašće Visoka škola ARCA, irena.mace@visokaskolaarca.hr

³ Doc.dr.sc. Mira Pavlinovic - Pomorski fakultet , Sveuciliste u Splitu, Mira.pavlinovic@pfst.hr

The tasks of inspection and personnel management are mainly related to tasks connected with control: Transport documents. Loading and unloading of cargo. Agency tariffs. Conditions for performing maritime agency activities. Ship exploitation agreements. Incoterms¹. Basics of trade and financial business².

In this research, the inspection and personnel managers from the following companies are interviewed and included in the survey:

1. Europe - Van Weelde, Rotterdam, Split Ship Management d.o.o. Agency, Jadroinspektor Koper Agency (Kopar)
2. USA - Southport Agencies Inc., Houston
3. China - SINO - Shipping Agency, Kosichang
4. South Amerika - Porto Agenciamontos, Santos (Brazil)
5. Singapore - Pacmar Ship Agency, Singapore

In Split, the costs that make up the total cost of the ship in the port (Disbursement account) are prescribed and issued by:

- Light Dues "Sjetlarina", Plovput
- Pilot in/out "Pilotaža", published by Pilot Split
- Berthing dues "berthing costs", Port Authority
- Port dues "port charges", Port Authority
- Mooring/Unmooring, Port Authority

Survey of inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs

1. For your job, personal involvement is also a challenge (how motivated, emotionally involved, and committed you are),
2. To what extent are inspectors and personnel in the maritime profession free to decide on the manner of carrying out their tasks, time for ideas (whether employees have time to think about things before they start acting),

¹ Incoterms, the official rules of the ICC (International Chamber of Commerce) for the interpretation of trade terms, have been in use worldwide for more than 60 years. Apart from the fact that these terms have become indispensable for the smooth conduct of international trade, their authenticity is recognized by all world courts and other administrative bodies, and their inclusion in sales contracts significantly reduces the possibility of misunderstandings that could lead to legal complications. In view of the changes and developments in trade practice, the ICC has released a new version of Incoterms, Incoterms 2000, which are in force from 1st January 2000.

² Place: Pomorsko učilište Adriamare Consulto d.o.o. ,Draga 2, Šibenik
(ex. Slobodna plovidba)

4. Is your work dynamic (fulfilment of organizational life with events), support for ideas (are there any means to test new ideas),
6. Is there trust and openness (do people feel confident to express their opinions and offer different points of view),
7. Is there excitement and humour (how relaxing is your workplace, is open-minded communication considered acceptable),
8. Are there any conflicts (to what extent do people get involved in interpersonal conflicts),
9. Are there discussions (to what extent do people engage in lively discussions on issues of real interest)
10. How much is risk-taking acceptable (is failure considered normal).

Empirical research

Isaksen and Kaufman¹ constructed the SOQ situational review questionnaire based on these guidelines. Based on the factor analysis, the dimension of dynamism was excluded, and the questionnaire was reduced to nine dimensions. This instrument contains 50 items and is designed to assess the extent to which each particular context supports creativity and change.

The goal of this research is the measurement of business creativity and the development of a creative organizational climate in the field of inspection and personnel management in maritime affairs.

The problem of this research can be formulated with the questions: How effective is an inspector and personnel manager who nurtures a creative business climate? Can cultivating the creative organizational climate in the reality of maritime economic organizations in practice increase the level of organizational creativity as a whole?

The answers to these questions are aimed at developing knowledge about the variables that enable the operationalization of the construct of the creative business climate as a factor in improving the effectiveness of education of inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs.

The set research goals were achieved by the following tasks:

¹ More details are available in: Jančićjević., N., (1996) *Organizacijska kultura - kolektivni um poduzeća* », ULIXES, Novi Sad, Ekonomski fakultet, Zagreb

- determining the possession of attitudes and the latent structure of attitudes of inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs towards the creative organizational climate;
- determining the nature of the connection between the social status characteristics of members of inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs (gender, experience, position, education ...) and their attitudes towards the creative organizational climate;
- discussing the results and drawing conclusions relevant to improving the effectiveness of management by fostering a creative organizational climate.

Research hypotheses

Ha1: The level of business-organizational creativity of inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs contributes to the improvement of the overall creativity of the management of maritime organizations, as well as the development of a creative organizational climate in the maritime business.

Research

The subject research is of an empirical nature. In the implementation of field research, the survey¹ method was used, as the basic methodological approach, to collect data with the help of several research instruments, which were processed, presented, and discussed by an appropriate statistical procedure. This method was chosen² because it proved to be a quite suitable method used for field determination of facts with this type of variables, especially when it comes to determining tendencies at the level of distributions and at the level of interconnectedness of obtained results on distributions of attitudes. The method of theoretical analysis was used as a supplementary method. The contents of scientific discussions and research dealing with the problems investigated in this paper are analysed³.

¹ It answers questions about how a large number of respondents feel, behave, etc., especially with regard to the time variable (how a specific population changes over time).

² Heinemann, Klaus (2003). "Uvod u metodologiju empirijskog istraživanja"

³ Gogala, Z., Šimičević, V. (2005.). "Korištenje statističkih metoda u hrvatskim poduzećima". Zbornik radova Ekonomskog fakulteta u Zagrebu, 3(1), 321- 339.

Research sample

The research sample was picked from all inspection and personnel managers in the maritime sector who completed their studies at the College of Inspection and Personnel Management¹. The sample was identified by random extraction by the method of systematic sampling (each n- from the list), with the original sample being the total number of surveyed organizations (it was expected that 20-30% of organizations would not provide valid survey material). A final sample from most companies with valid survey material was obtained. The sample was drawn based on the willingness of maritime inspection and personnel managers to cooperate. The survey process was conducted from September 2017 to January 2018. In the identified organizations, all members of maritime agents were defined as respondents.

The sample of respondents included 20 maritime inspectors and personnel managers by the end of the survey. The sample drawn in this way allows inference at the level of reliability $p < 0.05$.

Variables

An electronic survey and a survey with the help of interviewers (the VŠIKM associates) were used to collect data. The questionnaire contained the following sections:

1. Identification of observation units and respondents,
2. A battery of questions for identification of creativity climate in the organization,
3. A battery of questions about the subjective preferences, satisfaction, and proactive life attitude of members of inspection and personnel managers in the surveyed maritime organizations.

¹ This refers mostly to the students graduated from the College of Inspection and Personnel Management

Data processing

The data were entered into the basic matrix and subjected to multiple control (logical control, normality, requirements set by regression analysis, item analysis...). All variables were subjected to bivariate analysis (crossing with a dependently changeable variable). In accordance with the predominant nature of the data, a selection of statistical methods corresponding to the categorical data was made:

- Non-parametric tests - Hi square test,
- Logistic regression,
- Path analysis.

Depending on the nature of the data, other methods of analysis were applied (a graphical representation of variables for exploratory insight into the nature of distributions, etc.).

Research results

Reliability of variable systems

Before the analysis of data, it is necessary to determine to what extent the set of variables „hits” the construct that is the basis of the research, namely, the construct of organizational effectiveness and the construct of creativity. For this verification, an item analysis was performed, and a reliability test was applied by calculating the Cronbach's alpha¹.

The high value of Cronbach's alpha (Cronbach alpha: .966550) suggests high reliability of the variables used to include the constructs underlying this study.

The average correlation between variables is low ($r = 0.00$), which allows discrimination in identifying the relationship (relation) of individual variables. Detailed analysis of individual variables, their contribution to the reliability of the whole sample of variables, indicates the existence of variables whose exclusion from the sample of variables increases the value of Alpha (33 variables) and variables whose exclusion from the total sample of variables causes a decrease in Alpha (77 variables). The first category of variables has a lower value for explaining the cognitive content to which the overall research is oriented, while the second category has a high explanatory value.

¹ **Cronbach alpha: .966550** points to the conclusion of the high reliability of the variables used to include the constructs underlying this research.

The results of this test should be kept in mind when reducing a set of variables to a narrower set of factor variables.

Characteristics of the respondents

Before starting the analysis of the results obtained by the survey, it is necessary to determine the reliability of making conclusions based on statistical tests that represent the normality of the distribution of variables. If it turns out that the appropriate distribution of data with the least ordinal measurement scale is normal¹ (Gaussian curve), then stronger parametric tests can be applied, and if this is not the case, it is necessary to apply less strong parametric tests. The results of parametric tests applied to data that do not satisfy the premise of normality can be taken as an orientation in further analysis, but not as a reliable basis for reaching conclusions.

Analysis of demographic characteristics of respondents. The normality requirement is satisfied by a variable Work experience (RDIS8). Other variables do not meet this requirement, which must be taken into account when choosing statistical tests (shorter work experience). The absence of normality in the distribution of most variables limits the reliability of conclusions about the uniformity of the characteristics of respondents' attitudes, to which variation coefficients are indicated (except for the variable STRSP6, in which the variability deviation from the average values is over 50%).

The gender composition of the sample of respondents deviates from the natural gender structure of the population, but a ratio of 40:60 in favour of male respondents can be considered satisfactory for the social circumstances of Croatia.

Urban origin of respondents - Data indicate that 90% of respondents are of urban origin, while 10% come from rural areas.

This distribution of respondents is a consequence of intentional sampling appropriate to the requirements set by the topic of this paper - the requirement of research of inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs and its attitude towards creativity.

¹ The **normal distribution**, or **Gaussian distribution**, is an important family of continuous probability distributions, with applications in many fields. Members of the normal distribution family are defined through two parameters, *mathematical expectation*, and variance σ^2 .

The school education of the respondents (success in their studies) is one of the prerequisites of their ability to be involved in modern maritime processes, and especially to create a creative organizational climate. Since during the sampling, the respondents with the functions of members of the structures of inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs were selected, the data on their education shows that the subjective composition of inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs in selected organizations is prepared for tasks set by modern maritime management.

The work experience of the respondents measured by the years spent in employment shows that the respondents belong to the younger generations of professional inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs, and these two categories of respondents are almost equal - 51% vs. 48%. There are only three members of the older generation with over 20 years of work experience among the respondents.

Attitudes on the factors of professional development

Dimensions of professional development

Three following answers were offered to the question „Which dimension do you consider more important for professional development?“:

1. Subjective - which is manifested in the expressed abilities, self-confidence, interests, and attitudes, commitment to work, and other personal characteristics of the individual;
2. Objective - which is manifested in the objective conditions for professional advancement: the existence of jobs and positions that differ in complexity, responsibility, and organizational level;
3. They are equally important.

The analysis of the received answers shows that the respondents generally attach equal importance to the subjective and objective dimensions of professional development (three-quarters of the received answers).

This answer can be interpreted as an expression of insufficient immersion of respondents in the specific importance of the mentioned dimensions of professional development.

Based on the answers of a smaller number of respondents, who gave priority to one of the two dimensions, it can be stated that a relatively higher share of those who are turned to subjective

assumptions of professional development - 15%, concerning the personality of respondents and a much smaller share is of those who give priority to objective factors - 9%, which they cannot influence.

Characteristics of respondents important for successful professional development -

The question „In the following list, circle the number in front of the three characteristics that you consider most important for the successful professional development of an individual” had the task to lead respondents to define the priority of personality traits that contribute to successful professional development. Choosing from the eleven offered traits, the respondents singled out three traits they give priority to. Here is the list of offered features:

1. High intelligence
2. Nice physical appearance
3. Gender affiliation
4. Social origin and position of parents
5. Pleasant attitude towards people
6. Obedience and non-resentment
7. Moral integrity and independence
8. Work
9. Expertise
10. Reliance on connections
11. Entrepreneurship.

The analysis of the results showed that the three priority characteristics for the successful professional development of an individual are the following:

1. High intelligence - 37.4%
2. Work - 44.9%
3. Expertise - 49.2%.

To these abilities

- Moral integrity and independence - 22.1% and
- entrepreneurship - 26.8% can be added.

The respondents considered the following characteristics to be the least important: gender, social origin and position of parents, and reliance on relationships.

Based on these findings, it can be concluded that most respondents give priority to subjective characteristics that are subject to change if the individual is motivated for such a change and if cultural brakes do

not prevent the implementation of the necessary change in an individual's behaviour.

Willingness to engage in improving professional development -

Three following answers were offered to the question „How ready are you for intensive engagement (work, additional training, travel...) in order to improve your professional development?“:

1. I am not ready at all
2. I am mostly not ready
3. I am, and I am not ready
4. I am mostly ready
5. I am quite ready.

The data shows that three-quarters of respondents chose answers 4 and 5 on the scale - I am mostly ready and quite ready, and suggests that the jobs of inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs, whose work is analysed, are open to learning, which is an important condition for developing a creative organizational climate.

Analysis of correlation of variables

An indicative observation from the analysis of correlations is that with the growth of education, the readiness for efforts to further improve professional development decreases ($r_{sp} = 0.147$ with $p < 0.012$). With the increase in the urban environment in which the respondent grew up in childhood and early adolescence, the readiness for additional efforts for professional advancement increases ($r_{sp} = 0.122$ with $p < 0.037$). The same relation is observed in the positive correlation between the level of school education and readiness for additional professional advancement ($r_{sp} = 0.123$ with $p < 0.037$).

Satisfaction of respondents with the outcome and conditions of professional development

The respondents were asked about their satisfaction with the outcome and conditions of professional development.

1. Satisfaction with one's professional development.
2. Satisfaction with the general social conditions for the professional development of inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs.
3. Satisfaction with the attention paid to the development and motivation of staff in their work.
4. Satisfaction with the opportunity to acquire new professional skills through various educational programs.

Satisfaction with personal professional development is an aspect of the attitude of respondents towards themselves which, in 50% of respondents, shows the highest positive attitude (average level 3.93 with relatively lowest CV = 22.13%) (CV coefficient of variation), and in the other 25% the highest level satisfaction. Only 6.2% show extreme dissatisfaction in this regard.

The opposite attitude was shown by the respondents according to the general social conditions for the professional development of professionals and inspectors and personnel managers in maritime affairs (average level 2.86 with relatively highest CV = 39.51), with the proportion of respondents who show dissatisfaction with social conditions significantly higher - 36, 1%, of those who express a higher degree of satisfaction - 28.28.7%.

Satisfaction of respondents towards the situation in the organization, especially with the attitude of employers towards the development and motivation of staff, takes a central position on the satisfaction scale (average level is 3.42 with CV = 33.04%). It should be noted here that a significant percentage of respondents are undecided or dissatisfied - 47.7% - in assessing personnel policy in their organizations.

The same can be stated for respondents' level of satisfaction about the possibility of acquiring new professional or inspection skills through various educational programs (average level 3.40 with CV = 33.52). Nevertheless, 51.4% of respondents have above-average satisfaction with the possibility of education.

Analysis of correlation of variables

The analysis of the correlation of variables shows a high positive correlation between the variable Satisfaction with attention, which the organization dedicates to the development and motivation of maritime agents, and the variable Satisfaction with the opportunity to acquire new professional skills through various educational programs. There is also a strong correlation between the variable Satisfaction with one's professional development and the variable Satisfaction with attention, which is dedicated to the development and motivation of staff in the organization. It can be concluded that the respondents perceive the attention paid in the organization to the development and motivation of inspection and personnel managers

in the maritime sector as an important factor in creating a climate of satisfaction in their organizations.

Characteristics of the personality of the respondents

The respondents were asked ten questions with implicit introspective assessments of personality characteristics:

1. I am attracted to tasks or activities whose outcome depends on my abilities and efforts.
2. When I think about my success, I care more about meeting my inner criteria than comparing myself to others.
3. When I am not interested in any task, I try to do it as best I can.
4. I work on solving tasks, although they require more effort.
5. Dedicating a long time to one problem is a waste of time for me.
6. Problems that require a lot of effort and time attract me.
7. I like tasks or activities that require independence and responsibility.
8. The demands I make on myself in terms of the scope and quality of the work done are within the limits of what I can, know, and want.
9. I am indifferent if I do not carry out my work obligations.
10. I have the strength to do boring obligations well and on time.

The respondents were asked to express their estimates on the following measurement scale:

1. It never applies to me,
2. It rarely applies to me,
3. It sometimes applies to me,
4. It almost always applies to me, and
5. It always applies to me.

The respondents showed the highest level of assessment and mutual agreement (CV) in question 7.

I like tasks or activities that require independence and responsibility (this characteristic was identified in 81.6% of respondents) and

8. The requirements I set for myself in terms of the scope and quality of work done are within the limits of what I can, know, and want (82% of respondents).

Independence and responsibility are important characteristics of creative personalities.

Orientation to activities that rely on abilities and effort, as a characteristic of one's personality, was identified by 73.5% of respondents.

About three-quarters of respondents - 75% identified the characteristic of introversion - reliance on self-esteem without comparing their effects and success with others.

77.6% of respondents identified a tendency towards the increased effort in solving tasks at work.

The set of personal characteristics that the respondents identified at a slightly lower degree, but still at the level of „almost always applies to me” concerns the properties that are contained in the variables in questions 3, 5, 6, and 10.

The trait of self-control in a situation when the job requires boring, repulsive, and uninteresting tasks was identified by 68.9% of respondents, and over a quarter of respondents did not identify with this characteristic - 28%.

Another characteristic of self-control in a situation when the set task is not of respondent's interest was also identified by a high percentage of respondents - 71%. However, even with this characteristic, over one-quarter of the respondents - 27.8% failed to identify with this type of self-control.

The question that implies a negative attitude towards the persistence of problem-solving, contained in the variable Dedicate a long time to one problem for me is lost time, the respondents were divided into two approximately equal groups, 49.9% of those who identify with a reluctance to solve problems for a long time and those who identify such a long-term attachment to solving problems in themselves - 48.7%. The same question asked in a positive sense Problems that require a lot of effort and time attract me identified 57.6% of respondents - those who identify a tendency to long-term problem solving and 45% of those who do not find such a tendency. Finally, the question contained in the variable I am indifferent if I do not fulfil my work obligations was identified by 75.9% of respondents with grades that indicate their refusal to identify with indifference to the accepted obligations. There is the biggest disagreement among the respondents on this issue, which is indicated by the relatively highest coefficient of variation of 63.40%.

Relationship of subjective characteristics

An analysis of correlations within the batteries of subjective characteristics of respondents shows that the strongest positive correlation has variables When I am not interested in a task, I try to deal with it as best I can, and variable I'm working on solving tasks, although they require more effort.

Variable I am attracted to tasks or activities whose outcome depends on my abilities and efforts has a strong correlation with other variables of subjective characteristics of respondents:

- When I think about my success, I care more about meeting my inner criteria than comparing myself to others.
- I work on solving tasks even though they require more effort.
- I like tasks or activities that require independence and responsibility.
- The requirements I set for myself in terms of the scope and quality of work done are within the limits of what I can, know, and want.

The analysis of the creativity of inspectors and personnel managers in maritime affairs required the grouping of respondents included in the sample into categories according to the value processes attributed to all attitudes/statements calculated based on the scale applied in the questionnaire. The variable levelcreat was obtained by calculating the sum of the values attributed by each respondent to all the claims from the creativity questionnaire. However, this variable measures respondents' attitudes towards the level of creativity of the organizations in which these individuals work. For this research, it was important to assess the level of creativity for the organization, and it was necessary to determine the indicator of the level of creativity based on the average grades of all respondents from the same organization.

For this purpose, the average values of several respondents in the same organization were calculated (for most organizations with one respondent, the individual values were retained) and in this way, the variables KREORG1 and kreorg_rng were obtained (ranking of the organization in comparison with the average value of the KREORG variable where the value is 100 average values of all organizations).

¹ Kreorg 4r is an abbreviated name for the creativity of the observed organization for which the shipping agent works

Creativity level measurement scale:

- 0 - Completely not applicable
- 1 - Slightly applicable
- 2 - Largely applicable
- 3 - Fully applicable

Having in mind that the average assessment of the level of creativity, given by all respondents is 0.396 (median 0.428), it can be stated that in the sample of the observed organizations, the level of organizational creativity is at „zero” level, that ideas and behaviours are yet to be developed.

The analysis led to the finding that there is a connection between organizations and the level of organizational creativity.

This association is strong with a weak negative correlation. The Lambda test suggests that the level of organizational creativity is more influential in the organization than vice versa. This finding is significant because it points to the role of inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs as a subject of caring for the creative organizational climate. Such a climate is not born of itself, from the spontaneous initiative of employees, but represents the interest and action of the leading staff of the organization, especially the role of employers. According to the assumption based on literature and direct empirical insight, the subjective characteristics of participants in the practice of maritime companies are an important factor in the acceptance and development of relationships that characterize the creative organizational climate.

Verification of these hypotheses was performed by testing the correlation by grouping variables of organizational creativity with the subjective characteristics of the respondents.

The tests of the connection of all variables from the battery of subjective characteristics of the respondents confirmed that only SKOB4¹ school education is in a significant connection with the group variable Kreorg4r The level of creativity of the organization.

¹ SKOB – school education of inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs. The education variable measures the degree of education an individual has completed. This variable was also used in the cognitive engagement model, and it was explained and interpreted there.

The connectivity strength test indicates low levels of that connectivity. The Pearson's correlation coefficient¹ shows a weak negative correlation of the observed variables. The lambda test of the correlation direction of these variables confirms the justification of placing a group of variables in the position of the dependent variable (inference error is reduced by 9.4% versus 0% if the variable SKOB4 is placed in this position). These results point to the conclusion that school education is an important channel of intervention for employees in organizations in the direction of their orientation towards creative behaviour. The relatively insufficient level of school education of the respondents shows that there is a human factor inclined to accept the demands of creativity, but that there is no necessary interest in management structures to encourage such a tendency. A more detailed insight into the connection of the Kreorg4r² variable group with the dimensions of creativity points to the reasons for the mentioned absence of initiatives to create and develop a creative organizational climate in the observed organizations.

The process of selecting variables can be considered factors that contribute to the level of organizational creativity of the observed organizations. Special attention is demanded by a variable formulated by the statement "Fights over conspiracies, traps, over domination and territory, are common elements of life in the organization" which describes the climate opposite to that postulated as a creative organizational climate. A review of selected variables reveals that out of their total number, only two variables belong to a subset of positively formulated claims, and the rest include negative claims – respondents' assessments of the lack of creative climate in their organizations.

Identifying the factors that condition the existence and variation of levels of organizational creativity in the observed organizations has led to an insight into an important area of development of organizations and management in maritime affairs. The key finding of this research can be expressed by the following conclusion: in the

¹ Pirsonov koecijent korelacije predstavlja mjeru linearne ovisnosti jedne promjenljive o drugoj. Kvadrat Pirsonovog kvoecijenta korelacije predstavlja procent varijance jedne promjenljive koji druga promjenljiva objašnjava.

² Kreorg 4r is an abbreviated name for the creativity of the observed organization for which the inspector and personnel manager works.

sample of the observed organizations, the level of organizational creativity is at zero. Ideas and behaviours inherent in the creative organizational climate are just emerging (the average assessment of the level of creativity given by all respondents is 0.396, and the median is 0.428). To concretize this finding, an analysis of the relationship between groups of variables of organizational creativity with potential factor variables of organizational creativity was undertaken.

Conclusion of the empirical research

The results of this research show that inspection and personnel management is largely dissatisfied with current organizational practices and are therefore relatively often focused on adopting modern approaches to improving the effectiveness of inspection and personnel management, and their tendency to establish a creative organizational climate is positively correlated with management as a whole, as well as that the observed socio-experiential characteristics of inspection and personnel management belong to the system of determinants of their attitudes towards nurturing the climate of creativity. Finally, the personality characteristics of inspection and personnel managers have a significant impact on the formation of attitudes towards creativity. These findings imply that knowledge of the personality characteristics of members of maritime management structures can be a significant factor in achieving a high level of effectiveness of maritime management.

In concluding on the scope of this research, its limitations should be taken into account. The empirical part of the research encountered certain significant limitations in determining the sample - the choice of organizations in the sample could not be performed strictly in accordance with the requirement of chance.

Failure to respond of one part of inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs and organizations to the submitted survey material resulted in the deliberate selection of organizations that are willing to cooperate with researchers. This is certainly important when generalizing the conclusions drawn from the obtained research results.

To compensate for this limitation, we used the triangulation requirement when analysing the results. The results of this research confirm that the field of development of maritime organizations is

directed towards learning organizations - whose essential advantage over classic Taylor organizations is a creative organizational climate, openness to innovation of all kinds, and readiness for change management.

For the practice of development of inspection and personnel managers in maritime affairs, this research raises the problem of the embryonic state of organizational creativity and ways of its development to the level that enables these organizations as full competitors in the modern knowledge economy. The research has shown that fostering trust, accompanied by transparent measurement of processes and outcomes in current maritime organizations, can serve as a first step on the rise to highly effective maritime management.

The conclusions of the research show that, although there are significant differences between different program contents, the most important competencies are the ability of graduate students to analyse and synthesize and the ability to solve problems. There is a significant correlation between the opinions of graduates on the importance of general competencies for employability, on the necessity of acquiring them during their studies, and on the rank of individual competencies; the most important competencies are the ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, the ability to adapt to new situations, the pursuit of quality, information handling, independence, ability to work in a team, communication skills and interpersonal skills¹.

References

- Finch, L., Maddux, R. B. (2006). Delegation Skills for Leaders: An Action Plan for Success as a Manager. Third edition. Boston: Thomson.
- Gogala, Z., Šimičević, V. (2005). Korištenje statističkih metoda u hrvatskim poduzećima. Zbornik radova Ekonomskog fakulteta u Zagrebu, 3(1), 321- 339.
- Heinemann, Klaus (2003). Uvod u metodologiju empirijskog istraživanja, Stanford.
- Janićijević, N., (1996). Organizacijska kultura - kolektivni um poduzeća, ULIXES, Novi Sad, Ekonomski fakultet, Zagreb

¹ Finch, L.; Maddux, R. B. (2006). Delegation Skills for Leaders: An Action Plan for Success as a Manager. Treće izdanje. Boston: Thomson.